

D4.1: Map of data practices

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Documents used in the preparation of this deliverable:

- EPPN2020 Data management plan: https://eppn2020.plant-phenotyping.eu/Data_Policy
- Data management H2020: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Executive Summary

Objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to map the current information systems and data management practices used in plant phenotyping installations and national infrastructures. The map of existing information systems is the base for identifying both the adequate level of abstraction that will allow connection between related variables at different scales and the minimum requirements needed for inclusion in an EMPHASIS information system.

Main results

The data management landscape in European plant phenotyping facilities is highly heterogeneous but in progress. At the beginning of EMPHASIS prep, there were as many methods to handle phenotypic data and metadata as there are plant phenotyping infrastructures. However, a common effort with the companion project EPPN2020 results in information systems as integrative as possible to specifically handle plant phenotypic data following FAIR rules. Briefly, large effort needs to be dedicated to the identification of plants, sensors and objects that are involved in experiments, in a persistent way that makes them "Findable" (FAIR). Data storage, as it stood at the beginning of EMPHASIS-PREP was closer to satisfying the "Reusable" rule, although datasets are most often not "Accessible". Metadata are stored in most infrastructures, although in a way that is only accessible by humans and not machine readable, thereby making difficult data "Reuse". The same applies to the way how traits were named, whereas international initiatives allow rapid progress in this topic. In most places, information systems were in their infancy at the beginning of the project, and still less "Interoperable". Rapid progress also occurs in this topic with the deployment of local information systems developed in the EMPHASIS community, which follow FAIR principle and are compatible with those of the genomic and of the modelling communities, and with the involvement of EMPHASIS in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

1. Introduction

1.1. Data management in phenomics

Gathering phenomic data is currently expensive and time consuming, but technical advances can increase phenomic throughput and lower costs (1). Increasingly large numbers of plant traits need to be accurately measured in order to support and accelerate progress in breeding for novel traits, and although plant phenotyping technology evolves rapidly, parallel efforts are still required because large-scale phenotyping demands accurate reporting of at least a minimum set of information concerning experimental protocols, data management schemas, and integration with modeling (2). A feature of phenomic data is that plants bearing the same genotype but grown in different environment can completely differ in architecture, size, physiology and performance. Because environmental conditions largely vary over time and location, it is essential that local environmental data (as sensed by each plant) are collected together with any phenomic data and that metadata allow one to relate the genotype, the measured traits and the time course of environmental conditions sensed by the considered plant or plot (3). Such data organization is not reachable by using standard procedures such as lab books and spreadsheets. Reusability or non-reusability of plant phenotyping experiments are a direct result of data management practices: rich standardized metadata and interoperability among data providers are key components to the reproducibility of these experiments and their associated data analysis (4).

The present document presents the results of two consecutive studies directed by the work package 4 of EMPHASIS-PREP that shows the diversity of data management practices across European plant phenotyping structures.

1.2 FAIR Guiding Principles, EPPN²⁰²⁰ levels of data management and involvement of EMPHASIS in EOSC

The FAIR Guiding Principles are defined by the potential of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of the produced data and its resulting scientific results. Both data and analytical pipelines benefit from application of these principles (5).

We classified data management practices across European plant phenotyping infrastructures making use of the data policy designed in the companion project EU EPPN²⁰²⁰ https://eppn2020.plant-phenotyping.eu/Data_Policy, which designed two levels at which every local installation is in relation

to the FAIR Guiding Principles about how data is stored, how it is organized, what ownership rules apply to it and with which formats it is published.

Data storage should be organized in duplicated archives, with regular backups performed (“level 1” requirement). In order to match level 2 requirements, data storage should satisfy to the level 1 requirement and also comply with the following statements:

- Data is stored on a reliable cloud such as the European Grid Infrastructure
- Raw data is preserved at least 10 years (in order to enable re-analyses)
- Elaborate data is preserved ‘for ever’ (in order to enable meta-analyses)

Data organization should at least rely on Persistent Resource Identifiers: the identification and names of all objects involved in trans-national access experiments (e.g. plants, sensors or images) standardized, unambiguous and persistent. This is known as the “level 1” requirement regarding data organization. In addition, the level 2 requires technology and semantic interoperability, which can be provided by the use of ontologies.

Rules for data format. The level 1 data management practices require to avoid proprietary file formats and formats with rapid obsolescence (e.g. .xls or .xlsx file extensions). In addition to being non-proprietary, the preferred data formats satisfy the following characteristics:

- open, documented standard
- common usage by the research community
- standard representation (ASCII, Unicode)
- unencrypted
- checksum to ensure integrity

EMPHASIS is actively involved in the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**, specifically in the EOSC-Life project that aims at enabling ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by linking data management in biological research infrastructures. Specifically EMPHASIS is involved in a demonstrator within the EOSC-Life project called A+ that will link different life science infrastructures (EMPHASIS, ELIXIR, ISBE) by enabling the use and analysis of genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and phenotyping datasets of tomato, potato and maize. The goal is to compare drought, photosynthesis parameters, enzyme activities, biochemical traits as well as perform a detailed characterization of genetic, genomic data as well as expression profiles.

2. Methods

The present report draw it conclusions from interviews and a subsequent survey with more detailed questions. They were conducted in countries belonging to the EMPHASIS-PREP-group, plus Austria, Czech Republic, Finland and Poland (Figure 1). It is noteworthy that the mapping presented here represents the situation at the beginning of EMPHASIS-PREP. In each paragraph, an update is provided about the progress since then, largely with the action of the EPPN²⁰²⁰ project. The content of this survey is available online: <https://emphasis-eppn2020.shinyapps.io/information-systems-survey/>

Figure 1: Number of interviews per country, synthesizing two waves of surveys, a first one more general and a second one with more specific questions.

3. Map of information systems

3.1 Data storage

3.1.1 Database Management System

Figure 2: Data storage architecture: Which tools are you currently using for data handling and storage (first survey)

Data storage type is variable across the European plant phenotyping infrastructures (Figure 2). Most infrastructures rely on local solutions to store collected data, in many cases via spreadsheets. These systems are not interoperable, and subject to obsolescence of formats. Other infrastructures rely on SQL database management systems, which are standardized and therefore more likely to provide technology interoperability.

The same data storage type frequencies have been observed in the detailed survey that followed the first round of interviews (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Data Management Systems used for data storage

Overall, at the beginning of the EMPHASIS, only six local infrastructures were using a storage system that ensures that data will be available for the scientific community over years. A considerable effort still needed to be dedicated to reach a minimum level corresponding to level 1 of EPPN²⁰²⁰. Progress has been achieved since then, as all EPPN²⁰²⁰ local infrastructures now reached level 1.

3.1.2 Computer infrastructure

Most infrastructures rely on servers to manage and process plant phenotyping data (level 1), and some can additionally benefit from distributed systems (level 2) such as cloud or grids (Figure 4). However, many Infrastructures use neither of these tools and rely on personal computers for data analysis, as suggested by the survey that has been created following the first round of interviews (Figure 5). Hence, only in few places were data analyses accessible to researchers that were not associated with the experiments. The diffusion of workflows used on clouds is currently improving this feature, although a long way is still needed for reproducible and accessible data analysis.

Figure 4: Which computer infrastructure are you using for data handling and storage?

Figure 5: Tools used for data processing

In most places, data are duplicated in different locations, thereby providing a sufficient security for datasets (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Is data duplicated and stored in different location?

3.1.3 Status of tools and information systems

Information stored with proprietary tools and information systems could with time become impossible to retrieve. Indeed, the companies commercializing information systems can run out of business and no longer assure the maintenance of their systems, in opposition with the "findable" and "accessible" requirements of FAIR. Fortunately, there is little reliance on proprietary information systems among answers (figure 7). However, this does not indicate whether proprietary tools are used for subsequent data analysis or data sharing.

Figure 7: Reliance on proprietary information systems: Are you using a proprietary information system?

National infrastructures have developed FAIR-compatible phenomic information systems, which were then developed and diffused in the companion project EPPN²⁰²⁰ (6-8). These information systems allow organizing the data originating from images and sensors, together with maps of environmental data in the considered field or indoor installation and metadata describing, for instance, the x-y position of each plot or plant, thereby allowing one to relate phenotypic measurements to the local environmental conditions sensed by corresponding plants. The use of semantic web allow them to relate all objects of a given experiment, thereby allowing automatic generation of meta data. They are open source, available to the whole phenomic community and allow access to datasets for any scientist who holds the rights to consult it (depending on consortium agreements of corresponding projects). These new systems were still a minority in the plant phenotyping landscape at the beginning of EMPHASIS-PREP, even though they were more common than the reliance on a single commercial information system (Figure 8). This situation has largely improved with the development of the above mentioned phenomic information systems and their deployment in ten local infrastructures

Figure 8: Information system categories: which category of information system do you use?

3.1.4 Storage capacity

Figure 9: Storage capacity in terabyte what is the storage capacity of your computer infrastructure ?

Most infrastructures have medium or unknown storage capacity whereas others produce tens of terabytes of data every year (Figure 10). The amount of data produced in 2017 gives an insight on the amount of data generated in a typical year, even though many installations were at their beginning at the time of the survey.

Figure 10: Yearly rate of data production in Terabytes

3.1.5 Long-term data storage

Using an existing archiving capacity or designing one in order to implement the long-term storage rules of an infrastructure is a good indicator of a given infrastructure efforts towards good data management practices. It results that two thirds of the surveyed local infrastructures have designed a long-term archiving capacity (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Long-term data storage: have you designed a long-term archiving capacity?

3.2 Data exchange practices

3.2.1 Web services and the Breeding API initiative

Less than half of the studied infrastructures rely on Web Services for data exchange, either internally or for external data access (Figure 12). Many data exchange still operate via email or external hard drives, which limit the possibility to successfully and painlessly track the origin of scientific results (Figure 13). Only a handful of infrastructures display the use of Web Services database client systems which comply with the FAIR Guiding Principles.

Figure 12: Data accessibility through web services: are data available through webservicees?

Figure 13: Data exchange tools

The Breeding API (BrAPI) is a standardized web service API specification, facilitating interoperability among plant breeding applications in the field of plant breeding (8). Most European plant phenotyping infrastructures are not involved in BrAPI development, but some infrastructures started to or have successfully managed to implement it (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Degree of proximity with the Breeding API

The Breeding API emerging standard has been adopted in PIPPA (9), in PHIS (6) and in GnpIS (10).

3.2.2 External services

Most of the studied infrastructures do not use external services to share their data (Figure 15). The few infrastructures that do use external services cited the following ones:

- B2SHARE, a service provided by EUDAT as a reliable and trustworthy way for researchers, scientific communities and citizen scientists to store and share small-scale research data from diverse contexts
- B2SAFE, a service which allows community and departmental repositories to implement data management policies on their research data

- ePIC (Persistent Identifiers for eResearch): <https://www.pidconsortium.eu/>

Figure 15: Data findability and accessibility through external services: are you using external services for data sharing?

Other services are used in the studied plant phenotyping infrastructures:

- DOI system: <http://www.doi.org/>
- Cloud storage service for Dutch education and research: <https://www.surfdrive.nl/en> and SURFsara: <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/>
- FranceGrilles: <http://www.france-grilles.fr/presentation-en/fg-infrastructure/>
- iRods: <https://irods.org/>

Sharing data requires having previously set rules on data access, which is the case in most infrastructures encompassed in the online survey results (Figure 16). Two thirds of the infrastructures that have set up rules on data access have set up rules that are compatible with the EPPN²⁰²⁰ rules on data access.

Figure 16: Where rules set for data sharing and data access?

3.3 Data provenance and metadata

3.3.1 Identification systems

Most installations use a standardized identification system, which is necessary to reach EPPN²⁰²⁰ level 1 of data management practices (Figure 17). However identification is not sufficient for the "Findable" requirement of FAIR. For instance, a micro-plot of wheat can be referred to with an alias that makes sense for researchers involved in the experiment, e.g. "plot A2", but the same identifier is probably used in other experiments. Identifying plants, fields and other types of scientific objects using a standardized system such as DOIs is crucial to keep track of data provenance in the long term.

Figure 17: Usage of standardized identification systems

In the second survey, new questions were asked to evaluate the degree to which identifiers are persistent and uniform: “Which resources are associated with each of these identifiers?” The result is that only two installations are using identifiers that can be considered as persistent (Figure 18). A large effort is currently dedicated to this aspect in the project EPPN²⁰²⁰

Figure 18: Standard identification systems: incremental ID, primary key, RFID or NFC, URI, DOI (all Digital Object Identifiers are persistent) and PID (Persistent Identifier).

3.3.2 Standardized languages for metadata

Phenotypic datasets such as time series and plant images display metadata. Metadata on how data has been produced can be either minimal (a date, a location, and a method described briefly) or more extensive, with the inclusion of detailed experimental protocols and the analysis pipelines used to process data. Metadata can either be stored in a way that makes it intelligible only to humans (e.g. laboratory notebook, spreadsheets or in datasets folder names that include location and dates) or in a way that make them also machine-readable, i.e. through the use of standardized languages such as Dublin Core for documents. Only a third of the European plant phenotyping infrastructures use such standardized languages to organize metadata (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Usage of standardized languages for organizing metadata

Figure 20: Standardized languages used for organizing metadata

As shown in the survey that followed the 2018 interviews, metadata is stored either on human-readable only documents such as PDFs or text documents, either with languages that can potentially make them machine readable, such as CSV or RDF (Figure 20). The verbatim of the interviews gives a deeper knowledge of the standardized languages used to structure metadata. ISA-tab formats are used to organize metadata at IPK, in the framework of the MIAPPE project (11). Databases implementing MIAPPE are not only the IPK (and DPPN) data repository, but also CyVerse Data Common Repository and GnpIS (12). The metadata language is directly linked to where metadata is stored. If metadata is not saved using a standardized language, then it is stored in notebooks or text files, whereas if it is organized with a standardized language, then it is more likely to be stored in more suitable locations such as EPPN2020 level 1 compliant files or advanced shared databases (e.g. RDF triplestores). The more common metadata storage locations are files (compliant or non-compliant to EPPN²⁰²⁰ level 1 in the same proportions) and shared databases (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Metadata location

Half of the studied infrastructures is not implementing MIAPPE rules, while the other half is either trying to implement them, either directly involved in the MIAPPE community (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Degree of proximity with MIAPPE/PPEO

3.3.3 Standardized languages for data

When referring to a trait, one should rely on an unambiguous term through at least a local controlled vocabulary or at best a reference ontology. The MIAPPE community also suggests using ontologies such as PO, PATO and ENVO (11). Most phenotypic infrastructures use local vocabularies to label collected data, but fail to link those local vocabularies to reference ontologies (Figure 23). Relying on local vocabularies is however a first step towards the implementation of the FAIR principles.

Figure 23: Controlled vocabulary used for collected data

Controlled vocabularies are primarily used for traits, but are also used when labelling environmental variables, events (such as a pest attack), and for half of the studied infrastructures, for scientific objects (Figure 24). It is a good practice to rely on controlled vocabularies. For example, experimental data on plant height would not only contain the ambiguous label “plant height in meters” but would refer to a controlled vocabulary element whose label could also be “plant height in meters” but which would contain additional information such as how is this trait measured, with which tools and protocol. Additionally, this element could also be linked to a similar concept in a reference ontology.

Figure 24: Usage of a controlled vocabulary by data type

Conclusion

The data management landscape in European plant phenotyping facilities was highly heterogeneous at the beginning of this project. A common feature in most infrastructures was the combined use of local tools for data management and storage, not compatible with the FAIR principles. However, some groups have worked on building information systems as integrative as possible to specifically handle plant phenotypic data, in the frame of the European project EPPN²⁰²⁰.

The European plant phenotyping community expects EMPHASIS to promote the harmonization (of data, metadata, methods, data exchange protocols ...) through flexible standards. The upstream work carried out before writing this deliverable and resulting in the interviews presented in this document provided an environment favourable to the promotion of good data management practices through the notion of EPPN²⁰²⁰ “level” of plant phenotyping data management. The aim of those interviews and surveys was not only to check how advanced each plant phenotyping infrastructure is as to promote the benefits of upgrading one’s data management system in order to aim at respecting the FAIR Guiding Principles.

The work conducted by the WP4 of EMPHASIS-PREP provides an environment propitious to the diffusion of good data management practices. Even though most European plant phenotyping infrastructures still do not meet those standards, awareness about them increases. There is also within the community the realization of the benefits that could offer the adoption of standards such as MIAPPE for data and metadata and BrAPI for data exchange through Web Services. The diversity of data management systems throughout the plant phenotyping landscape makes it difficult to find one tool shared by all infrastructures and that could be used for data exchange between those infrastructures. The flexibility provided by Web Services can be exploited for data exchange in the community. The collaboratively developed standard BrAPI provides a good starting point for such data exchange. Regarding what is exchanged, data and metadata, the MIAPPE initiative set the basis for the minimal information to provide.

The next step for the EMPHASIS-PREP WP4 is to diffuse local information systems developed in the companion project EPPN²⁰²⁰, together with rules for data storage and ontologies that make the data management practices evolve towards the FAIR Guideline Principles. Intense discussions are under way with other infrastructures, such as ELIXIR, ANaEE and AGMIP to make the phenomic information accessible to other communities, namely in genomics, in ecology and in crop modelling.

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